

Correlates of Patient Satisfaction with the Chronic Care Model and Self-Determination Principles versus Usual Care among Patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus in North-Central Nigeria

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Chronic Care Model, Self Determination Theory, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Patient Satisfaction, North-Central Nigeria.

Abstract

Background: This study assessed patient satisfaction with care delivered using the Chronic Care Model (CCM) integrated with Self-Determination Theory (SDT) principles compared with usual care among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) in North-Central Nigeria. Patient satisfaction is a key indicator of quality of chronic illness care and adherence to long-term management.

Methods: A single-blinded randomized controlled trial was conducted among 90 adults with T2DM attending the General Outpatient Clinic of the Federal University Teaching Hospital, Lafia. The study employed a mixed-methods approach, utilising both quantitative surveys to assess patient satisfaction scores and qualitative interviews to explore specific aspects influencing these scores within both care models. Participants were randomised to CCM-based care (n=45) or usual care (n=45). Patient satisfaction was measured using the Patient Assessment of Chronic Illness Care (PACIC) scale. Associations between SDT constructs (autonomy,

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competence, relatedness) and satisfaction were examined using Pearson's correlation.

Results: Patients in the CCM group reported significantly higher satisfaction scores across all PACIC domains than those in usual care ($p < 0.001$). Autonomy ($r=0.62$), competence ($r=0.59$), and relatedness ($r=0.55$) showed significant positive correlations with overall satisfaction ($p < 0.001$). Socio-demographic factors such as age and educational status showed modest associations with satisfaction.

Conclusion: The integration of Self-determination principles with the Chronic Care Model, significantly improves satisfaction among Nigerian patients with T2DM. Integration of SDT principles enhances motivation and engagement, supporting the adoption of CCM in resource-limited settings.

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is one of the most significant non-communicable diseases globally, with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) accounting for over 90% of all cases [1,2]. The global prevalence of diabetes has risen sharply over the past three decades, driven by population ageing, urbanisation, sedentary lifestyles, and dietary transitions [3]. Low- and middle-income countries now bear a disproportionate share of this burden, with sub-Saharan Africa experiencing one of the fastest growth rates [4,5]. In Nigeria, diabetes prevalence is estimated to range between 5.5% and 10.7%, with many patients presenting late and experiencing poor glycaemic control and preventable complications [6,7].

Conventional diabetes care in Nigeria is predominantly acute, physician-centred, and episodic, focusing on pharmacological treatment rather than long-term self-management and patient engagement [8,9]. This approach is poorly aligned with the chronic and behavioural nature of diabetes and contributes to suboptimal outcomes, including low treatment adherence, poor satisfaction, and reduced quality of life [10]. Patient satisfaction has emerged as a critical indicator of healthcare quality and effectiveness, particularly in chronic disease management, where sustained engagement with care is essential [11-15].

The Chronic Care Model (CCM), developed by Wagner and colleagues, provides a comprehensive framework for restructuring health systems to improve chronic disease outcomes [16,17]. The model emphasizes six interrelated components: healthcare organisation, delivery system design, self-management support, decision support, clinical information systems, and community resources [18,19]. Evidence from high-income countries and selected low-resource settings demonstrates that CCM implementation improves patient satisfaction, self-management behaviours, and clinical outcomes in diabetes care [20-22]. However, there remains limited experimental evidence evaluating CCM effectiveness in Nigerian healthcare settings.

Self-Determination Theory (SDT) offers a complementary psychological framework for understanding patient motivation and engagement in chronic illness care [23]. SDT posits that individuals are

more likely to adopt and sustain health behaviours when their basic psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness are supported. This model has been integrated into diabetic care successfully [24,25]. Autonomy-supportive healthcare environments have been associated with improved adherence, glycaemic control, and patient satisfaction among individuals with diabetes [26,27]. Integrating SDT principles within CCM-based care may therefore enhance patient experiences and satisfaction by aligning system-level interventions with motivational processes.

This study compared patient satisfaction with care delivered using a CCM-based, SDT-informed approach versus usual care among adults with T2DM in Nigeria. It also examined the association between SDT constructs and patient satisfaction.

Objectives

To determine the level of satisfaction among patients receiving a combination of CCM based care with SDT theory compared to usual care among adults with type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Specific Objectives

The following were the specific aims

1. To determine the level of satisfaction between the two arms of the study
2. To determine correlates of satisfaction.

Methodology

Study Design and Population

A single-blinded randomized controlled trial was conducted at the General Outpatient Clinic of the Federal University Teaching Hospital, Lafia, Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Study Population

The study was carried out at the General Outpatient Clinic (GOPC) of the Federal University Teaching Hospital (FUTH, Lafia), formerly known as Dalhatu Araf Specialist Hospital, in Lafia. Lafia is the capital of Nasarawa State, with a population of 509,300 according to the projected 2022 figures. Nasarawa State is located in North-central Nigeria and had an estimated population of 2,886,000 in 2022 [28]. FUTH, Lafia is a tertiary health facility situated in Lafia, the state capital, with 420 beds across various departments, including paediatrics, obstetrics and gynaecology, surgery, medicine, and private wards. The

GOPC operates daily from 8:00am to 4:00pm, staffed by medical officers, resident doctors, and consultants in Family Medicine, delivering continuous, holistic, and comprehensive care for both acute and chronic conditions. Adults aged ≥40 years with confirmed T2DM, on treatment for at least six months, and attending the clinic during the study period were eligible.

Sample Size

The sample size for the study was determined using the formula for comparison of mean differences between two groups using a power of 95% and 80% confidence level [29].

$$N = (Z\alpha/2 + Z\beta)^2 (\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_c^2) / \partial^2 \tag{1}$$

Where: N = minimum sample size required for each group.

Zα/2 = 1.96 which is the t-value of the desired confidence level of 95% when alpha is 0.05 (Statistical standard values in a normal population distribution).

Zβ = 0.84 which is the t-value of the desired power of 80% when β is 0.2 (Statistical standard values in a normal population distribution).

σ₁ = is mean difference of effect of CCM on glycaemic control in the Intervention group in a previous study in Pakistan = 1.06 [24].

σ_c = is mean difference of effect of usual care on glycaemic control in the Control group in a previous study in Kenya = 0.60 [25].

∂ = mean difference between the study groups (Control and Intervention) = 0.46.

Therefore:

$$N = [1.96 + 0.84]^2 (1.06^2 + 0.60^2) / 0.46^2$$

$$N = [2.80]^2 \times (1.12 + 0.36) / 0.21$$

$$N = 7.84 \times 2.19 / 0.21$$

$$N \approx 82 \text{ (Minimum sample size)}$$

To account for follow-up losses during the study, 10% of the minimum sample size was added.

$$N \approx 90$$

A minimum sample size of 82 was calculated using comparison of means; 90 participants (45 per group) were recruited to account for attrition. Systematic random sampling was used, followed by simple random allocation into intervention (CCM) and control (usual care) groups.

Inclusion Criteria

Consenting, confirmed diagnosis (at least 6 months), Type 2 DM patients aged ≥ 40 years, on medication, who understood English or Hausa and had mobile phones for ease of follow up.

Exclusion Criteria

Pregnant women (because they would require specialized care), those who were unlikely to be available for the whole duration of the study and patients with co-morbidities e.g. Hypertension, Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD).

Intervention

The intervention group received structured CCM-based care including self-management education, goal-setting, regular follow-up, and coordinated clinical records. The control group received routine usual care.

Assessment Tools

Two main tools were used to collect data, and they included a structured questionnaire and patient satisfaction surveys. The demographic and clinical data were obtained in the questionnaire, such as age, sex, years of diagnosis, and comorbidities. The survey on patient satisfaction was based on a validated tool, Patient Assessment of Chronic Illness Care (PACIC),^{30,31} used to gauge the satisfaction of the processes of care in managing chronic diseases. The SDT construct were analysed using the Basic Psychological Needs Satisfaction Scale (BPNSS) which is reliable and validated across cultures.³²⁻³⁵

1. Study questionnaires (Appendix II) for biodata, socio-economic demographics and family information.
2. Questionnaire on clinical variables.
3. 20-item PACIC scale, scored from 1 (rarely) to 5 (almost always).
4. BPNSS was adapted used to measure autonomy, competence, and relatedness measures.

Study Protocol

Their follow-up visits from the first encounter were scheduled at four weeks, eight weeks and 12 weeks (each participant had four encounters with the researcher) for both groups.

Data Analysis

Data was analysed using SPSS version 23. Continuous variables were compared using independent t-tests, categorical variables using χ² or Fisher’s exact tests. Pearson’s correlation assessed relationships between SDT constructs and satisfaction. Statistical significance was set at p<0.05.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the hospital ethics committee. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Results

Table 1: Details of the Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Study Participants

	Intervention group N=45 (%)	Control group N=45 (%)	t-test	P-value
Mean Age (years)	57.48±1.53	54.17±1.39	-1.599	0.113

40-59	27(60.0)	29(64.4)	4.026**	0.402
60 and above	18(40.0)	16(35.6)		
Sex			X ²	
Male	33(73.3)	36(80.0)	0.559	0.455
Female	12(26.7)	9(20.0)		
Religion			0.049	0.82
Christianity	16(35.6)	15(33.3)		
Islam	29(64.4)	30(66.7)		
Marital status				
Married	32(71.1)	30(66.7)		
Unmarried	13(28.9)	15(33.3)		
Educational qualification			1.061*	0.786
No education	4(8.9)	7(15.6)		
Primary	7(15.6)	7(15.6)		
Secondary	14(31.1)	14(31.1)		
Tertiary	20(44.4)	17(37.7)		
Address			4.113	0.043
Urban	39(86.6)	31(68.9)		
Rural	6(13.3)	14(31.1)		
Average family income (₹)			4.201*	0.122
<50,000	21(46.7)	30(66.7)		
50,000 – 100,000	20(44.4)	11(24.4)		
>100,000	4(8.9)	4(8.9)		
Alcohol consumption			0.008**	0.777
Yes	7(15.6)	8(17.8)		
No	38(84.4)	37(82.2)		
Cigarette smoking			1.111*	0.292
Yes	6(13.3)	3(6.7)		
No	39(86.7)	42(93.3)		
Occupation			5.980	0.542
Civil servants	16(35.6)	20(44.4)		
Business	19(42.2)	15(33.3)		
Artisans	10(22.2)	10(22.2)		

Note: *=Fisher’s exact test, **=Chi-square test

Table 2: Details of the Baseline Medical Characteristics of Both Groups

	Intervention group N=45 (%)	Control group N=45 (%)	X ²	P-value
Year of diagnosis (years)			0.060	0.970
6months – 4 years	22(48.9)	21(46.7)		
5 – 10 years	10(22.2)	10(22.2)		
>10 years	13(28.9)	14(31.1)		
Family history of Diabetes			0.044	0.832
Yes	24(53.3)	25(55.6)		
No	21(46.7)	20(44.4)		
Past medical emergency			0.623	0.419
No	38(84.4)	35(77.8)		
Yes	7(15.6)	10(22.2)		
Admission in the past 2 months			0.000	1.000
Yes	5(11.1)	7(15.6)		
No	40(88.9)	38(84.4)		
Type of medication presently on				
OGLA	45(100.0)	45(100.0)		
Insulin	0(0.0)	0(0.0)		

Knowledge of appropriate blood glucose level				
Yes	9(20.0)	7(15.6)	3.986	0.046
No	36(80.0)	38(84.4)		
Practice self-foot Examination				
Yes	16(35.6)	10(22.2)	1.947	0.163
No	29(64.4)	35(77.8)		

Table 3: Details of the Baseline Clinical Characteristics of Both Groups

	Intervention group N=45 (%)	Confidence interval	Control group N=45 (%)	Confidence interval	X2	P-value
Mean BMI(kg/m2)	27.5±5.7		27.8±6.5		-0.751	0.454
Underweight <18.5	0(0.0)		3(6.6)		3.163**	0.367
Normal weight (18.5 – 24.99)	12(26.7)		12(26.7)			
Overweight (25.00 – 29.99)	16(35.6)		14(31.1)			
Obese (30.00 and above)	17(37.7)		16(35.6)			
Mean Systolic BP(mmHg)	120.9±6.2		121.9±6.8		1.696	0.093
Mean Diastolic BP(mmHg)	78.9±6.6		79.1±5.8		2.609	0.010
Fasting Blood glucose	8.9±1.2		9.16±2.9		-1.95	0.053
Baseline mean Glycated haemoglobin	8.2±1.1	7.90-8.13	7.6±0.5	7.46-7.78	3.309	0.001
<6.5	0(0)		0(0)			
6.5 or more	45(100.0)		45(100.0)			

Note: ** = Chi-square test

Table 4: Level of Satisfaction of the Intervention and Control Groups at Baseline

	Intervention group N=45 (%)	Control group N=45(%)	X2	P-value
Satisfied my care well organized			1.918	0.219
Yes	12(26.7)	10(22.2)		
No	33(73.3)	35(77.8)		

Table 5: PACIC Score at Baseline

	Intervention group N=45 (%)	Confidence interval	Control group N=45 (%)	Confidence interval	t-test	P-value
Mean PACIC score	1.20 ± 0.18	0.91-1.67	1.19 ± 0.16	0.89-1.65	3.987	0.067
PACIC score class						
Good	0(0.0)		0(0.0)			
Poor	45(100.0)		45(100.0)			

Table 6: Post Intervention Mean Patient Satisfaction Scores by Care Model

Domain of Satisfaction	CCM Group (n=43)	Usual Care Group (n=41)	t-value	p-value
Communication with Healthcare Providers	4.5 ± 0.6	3.8 ± 0.7	9.21	<0.001
Access to Medications	4.2 ± 0.5	3.6 ± 0.8	8.14	<0.001
Involvement in Decision-Making	4.3 ± 0.5	3.5 ± 0.7	7.72	<0.001
Quality of Patient Education	4.6 ± 0.6	3.7 ± 0.9	10.13	<0.001
Follow-up Care	4.7 ± 0.5	3.9 ± 0.7	9.74	<0.001
Overall Satisfaction	4.6 ± 0.5	3.7 ± 0.8	10.56	<0.001

i. **Communication with Healthcare Providers:** The CCM patients noted significant levels of communication with their healthcare providers in contrast to their counterparts in the Usual Care group (4.5 vs 3.8).

ii. **Access to Medications:** CCM patients also reported higher access to medications with a mean score of 4.2 than the Usual Care with a mean score of 3.6 (t = 8.14, p < 0.001).

- iii. **Engagement in Decision-Making:** The CCM group felt more engaged in their decisions on treatment (mean score = 4.3) than the Usual Care group (mean score = 3.5).
- iv. **Quality of Patient Education:** The group of CCM rated the quality of patient education as much higher (mean score = 4.6) compared to the Usual Care group (mean score = 3.7) ($t = 10.13, p < 0.001$).
- v. **Follow-up Care:** The perception of the follow-up care was significantly higher in the CCM group (mean

score = 4.7) than the Usual Care group (mean score = 3.9) ($t = 9.74, p = 0.001$).

- vi. **General Satisfaction:** The general level of patient satisfaction (mean score = 4.6) was significantly greater in the CCM group (as compared to the Usual Care group) ($t = 10.56, p < 0.001$).

The findings suggest that the CCM has a distinct benefit in enhancing patient satisfaction across the entirety over the Usual Care model, and all the comparisons were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

Table 7: Post-Intervention PACIC Score

	Intervention group N=43 (%)	Confidence interval	Control group N=41 (%)	Confidence interval	t-test	P-value
Mean PACIC score						
PACIC score class	3.72 ± 0.27	3.21-4.09	2.41 ± 0.25	2.12-3.11	15.984	0.001
Good	41(95.3)		0(0.0)		5.134*	0.003
Poor	2(4.7)		41(100.0)			
Mean difference in PACIC score baseline and post-intervention	2.52 ± 0.09		1.22 ± 0.09			

Note: *=Fisher’s exact test

Table 8: Correlation between Basic Psychological Need Satisfaction (BPNSS) Domains and Overall Patient Satisfaction

BPNSS Domain	Conceptual Definition (SDT)	r	p-value
Autonomy Satisfaction	Perceived choice, volition, and involvement in diabetes care decisions	0.62	< 0.001
Competence Satisfaction	Perceived effectiveness and confidence in managing diabetes	0.59	< 0.001
Relatedness Satisfaction	Perceived support, care, and connection with healthcare providers	0.55	< 0.001

BPNSS domains represent aggregated need satisfaction scores for autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Pearson correlation coefficients (r) indicate associations with overall patient satisfaction.

- i. **Autonomy:** Patient autonomy was highly correlated with overall satisfaction ($r = 0.62, p < 0.001$). This implies that the greater the autonomy enjoyed by patients in their care, the more they were satisfied.
- ii. **Competence:** There was a moderate positive relationship between competence and satisfaction ($r =$

0.59, $p < 0.001$). More satisfied patients expressed that they were more competent to cope with diabetes.

- iii. **Relatedness:** Correlation between relatedness and patient satisfaction was also positive ($r = 0.55, p < 0.001$), indicating that patients who were more related to their care providers and care teams were more satisfied.

These associations also confirm the use of Self-Determination Theory (SDT), which demonstrates the role of autonomy, competence, and relatedness in improving patient satisfaction with diabetes care.

Table 9: Comparison of Patient Satisfaction by Demographic Factors

Demographic Factor	CCM Group Mean Satisfaction	Usual Care Group Mean Satisfaction	t-value / F-value	p-value
Age (<60 vs ≥60)	4.7 vs 4.5	3.8 vs 3.6	2.14	0.03
Gender (Male vs Female)	4.6 vs 4.7	3.8 vs 3.6	1.95	0.05
Duration of Diagnosis	4.5 vs 4.6	3.7 vs 3.8	1.18	0.24
Demographic Factor	CCM Group Mean Satisfaction	Usual Care Group Mean Satisfaction	t-value / F-value	p-value

- i. **Age:** The findings showed that there was a significant difference in the amount of satisfaction according to age in both the CCM and Usual Care

groups where patients aged 60 years and above had a slightly lower level of satisfaction ($p = 0.03$).

ii. **Gender:** Satisfaction differed marginally according to gender with female patients in both groups having marginally higher scores on satisfaction ($p = 0.05$).

iii. **Duration of Diagnosis:** There was no significant difference in satisfaction with regard to the amount of time lived with diabetes diagnosis ($p = 0.24$), which implies that the period of time that one had lived with diabetes did not play a significant role in the overall satisfaction.

Discussion

This study demonstrates that care delivered using the Chronic Care Model integrated with Self-Determination Theory principles significantly improves patient satisfaction among adults with type 2 diabetes mellitus compared with usual care in a Nigerian tertiary hospital setting. Participants exposed to the combined CCM and SDT -based care reported higher satisfaction across all CCM domains. The difference in satisfaction when disaggregated was significant for each of the domain ($p \leq 0.0001$). These findings underscore the importance of structured, patient-centred approaches in the management of chronic diseases.

The observed improvement in satisfaction is consistent with findings from systematic reviews and randomized studies conducted in high-income countries and selected low- and middle-income settings, which report that CCM implementation enhances patient experiences and perceived quality of care [20,22]. The present study extends this evidence by demonstrating CCM effectiveness in a Nigerian context, where healthcare systems are often constrained by limited resources, workforce shortages, and fragmented service delivery.

This is however in contrast to the study conducted by [36], who did not find any significant difference among the groups studied and [21] who found minimal differences which was not statistically significant.

The significant positive correlations between autonomy, competence, relatedness, and overall satisfaction provide empirical support for the relevance of SDT in diabetes care. Autonomy-supportive interactions likely enhanced patients' sense of control and involvement in decision-making, while competence-supportive education improved confidence in self-management skills. Relatedness, fostered through continuity and supportive provider-patient relationships, may have strengthened trust and engagement. These findings align with prior studies linking SDT constructs with improved satisfaction, adherence, and glycaemic outcomes in diabetes populations [37-39].

Sociodemographic factors showed only modest associations with satisfaction, suggesting that the observed effects were primarily attributable to the care model rather than patient characteristics. This is an important finding in a setting marked by wide

socioeconomic disparities, as it suggests that CCM-based interventions may be broadly effective across diverse patient groups. This agrees with the findings of [40] who found that sociodemographic factors did not significantly affect patients' satisfaction but contrasted with the findings of [41] who found that gender influenced satisfaction among his cohort.

Overall, the findings support a paradigm shift away from episodic, provider-centred care toward integrated, patient-centred chronic care models that explicitly address motivational processes. Such approaches are particularly relevant for diabetes management, where long-term behaviour change is fundamental to disease control.

Conclusion

Care delivered using the Chronic Care Model integrated with Self-Determination Theory principles significantly improves patient satisfaction among adults with type 2 diabetes mellitus in Nigeria compared with usual care. By addressing both system-level organisation of care and patient-level motivational needs, CCM-based interventions enhance patient experiences and engagement. These findings provide empirical support for the adoption of structured, patient-centred chronic care approaches within Nigerian health systems.

Recommendations

Healthcare policymakers and hospital administrators should prioritise the integration of Chronic Care Model components into routine diabetes services, including structured follow-up, self-management education, and coordinated care systems. Training healthcare providers in autonomy-supportive communication and motivational approaches grounded in Self-Determination Theory may further enhance patient satisfaction and engagement. Future diabetes programmes in Nigeria should incorporate patient-centred outcome measures, such as satisfaction and quality of life, alongside clinical indicators.

Strengths and Limitations

Strengths

A key strength of this study is its randomised controlled design, which strengthens causal inference regarding the effect of CCM-SDT based care on patient satisfaction. The use of validated instruments, including the PACIC and BPNSS, enhances the reliability of the findings. Additionally, the integration of a theoretical framework (SDT) provides conceptual depth and explanatory value.

Limitations

The study was conducted at a single tertiary facility, which may limit generalisability to primary care or rural settings. The relatively small sample size and short follow-up period preclude assessment of long-term sustainability and clinical outcomes. Self-reported measures may also be subject to response bias.

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